

ENHANCING ENERGY SYSTEM RESILIENCE THROUGH ADVANCED TECHNOLOGICAL AND POLICY INTERVENTIONS

Abstract. The resilience of energy systems is critical for ensuring reliable energy supply amidst increasing challenges from climate change, natural disasters, and cyber threats. This study investigates the role of emerging technologies, such as edge computing, artificial intelligence (AI), and distributed energy resources (DER), alongside policy interventions in enhancing energy system resilience. Findings highlight the necessity of integrated approaches combining technical, economic, and regulatory measures to build adaptive and sustainable energy infrastructures.

Introduction. Energy systems worldwide face mounting challenges, including extreme weather events, rising energy demands, and the transition to renewable energy sources. Resilience is essential for these systems to adapt and recover from disruptions. Advanced technologies like edge computing and AI, paired with robust policy frameworks, can significantly enhance the resilience of energy systems. This paper explores these solutions and their implementation to address current and future challenges.

Methods. The research employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating:

1. Review of resilience-oriented frameworks incorporating emerging technologies such as edge computing and AI [1].
2. Case studies analyzing the role of distributed energy resources (DER) and mobile energy systems in enhancing operational flexibility [2].
3. Examination of policy interventions supporting energy resilience, including regulatory frameworks and incentive programs for renewable energy integration [3].

Results and Discussion.

1. Technological Interventions

1.1. Edge Computing and AI. Edge computing enables real-time data processing and decision-making, enhancing the operational resilience of energy systems [4]. AI-driven algorithms improve predictive maintenance and resource optimization, reducing downtime during disruptions [5].

1.2. Distributed Energy Resources (DER). DER enhances localized energy generation and distribution, reducing the dependency on centralized systems and providing critical support during outages [6].

2. Policy Interventions

2.1. Regulatory Frameworks. Policies promoting the adoption of DER and advanced technologies, such as tax incentives and subsidies for renewable energy systems, are crucial for fostering resilience [7].

2.2. Resilience Metrics and Standards. Establishing standardized resilience metrics aids in benchmarking and improving system performance under varying conditions [8].

3. Integrated Approaches

The combined application of technological and policy interventions shows significant potential in building adaptive and resilient energy systems. Case studies demonstrate reduced recovery times and improved reliability through the integration of edge computing, DER, and supportive policies.

Conclusion. Energy system resilience demands a holistic approach integrating advanced technological solutions and supportive policy frameworks. Edge computing, AI, and DER play a pivotal role in enhancing resilience, while policy interventions ensure the widespread adoption and integration of these technologies. Future efforts should focus on standardizing resilience metrics and fostering global collaboration to address the evolving challenges of energy systems.

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